

HOZIRGI KUNDA NASOS STANSIYALARIGA SUV OLIB KELUVCHI KANALLAR VA NASOS STANSIYALARIDAN FOYDALANISH MUAMMOSINING O'RGANILGANLIGI

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Annotatsiya: Respublikamiz hududida suv xo'jaligida tizimida ichki suv resurslari shakllanib boradi va shundan transchegaraviy suv resurslari ham mavjud, bunda foydalanish holatida noqulaylik tug'dirilayotgan bir qancha muammolar mavjud bularni bartaraf qilish uchun esa bir qancha ishlar olib borilmoqda bular ustida ko'pgina ilmiy ishlar, maqolalar shu muammoni hal etish maqsadida tayorlanib va ular yordamida o'zgarishlar olib borilib muammolar hal etilmoqda bu maqolaning ham mazmunu hozirgi kunda nasos stansiyalariga suv olib keluvchi kanallar va nasos stansiyalaridan foydalanish muammosining o'rganish uchun olib borilgan ishlar yoritilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: *magistral, deformatsiyasi, grunt, Grunt, suv xo'jaligi, xarakteristika, ekspluatatsiya.*

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Аннотация: Система водного хозяйства имеет решающее значение для управления водными ресурсами страны и обеспечения их эффективного использования. Хотя внутренние водные ресурсы формируются в нашей республике, важно также использовать трансграничные водные ресурсы. В то же время возникает ряд проблем трансграничного использования водных ресурсов. В основном это связано с разногласиями между государствами, владеющими водными ресурсами, по вопросам, касающимся распределения воды, справедливого и эффективного управления ею.

Для решения таких задач разрабатывается ряд научных разработок и технических подходов. Исследования и статьи в этой области направлены на управление водными ресурсами, улучшение систем водоснабжения и обеспечение экологической устойчивости. Рабочее состояние насосных станций также требует особого внимания. О проблемах с водоотводными каналами и насосными станциями

Ключевые слова: магистраль, деформация, грунт, Грунт, водное хозяйство, характеристика, эксплуатация.

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Annotation: On the territory of the Republic, internal water resources are formed in the water industry system, and from this there are also cross-border water resources, there are several problems that cause inconvenience in the case of Use, and a number of works are being carried out to eliminate these, many scientific works are being carried out on them, the articles are being

Keywords: noun, deformation, water farm, characteristic, exploitation.

As you know, on the territory of our republic, internal water resources are formed, and from this there are also cross-border Water Resources. Of this, 80% or more at the expense of the Amudarya and Syrdarya rivers will not be exaggerated.

In general, more than 80% of the total used water in the economy of our country corresponds to agricultural contributions and the rest – to the domestic service sector, energy, industry and Fisheries and other industries.

4.3 million irrigated in the Republic of Uzbekistan. ga provides more than 1,600 pumping stations and facilities to 53% of the arable land. In addition, water is supplied to agricultural land where water consumer associations and farms operate using more than 8,000 small pumping stations and devices

Currently, the “SUVMASH” plant, which produces pumping units in our republic, pump repair enterprises in the regions continue to operate.

АМУ-ҚАШҚАДАРЕ ИРРИГАЦИЯ ТИЗИМИДА ХАВЗА БОШҚАРМАСИ КУЗУРБАТИ НАСОС СТАНЦИЯЛАРИ ВА ЭНЕРГЕТИКА БОШҚАРМАСИ		
1	ИШГА ТУШГАН ЙИЛИ	1981 ЙИЛ
2	ЎРНАТИЛГАН АГРЕГАТ СОНИ	3 ДОНА
3	НАСОС ТУРИ	22 НЦС
4	СУВ ЧИҚАРИШ ҚОБИЛИЯТИ	1,1 М3/СЕК.
5	ЭЛЕКТРОДВИГАТЕЛЬ ТУРИ	СД2-85-67-2УМ
6	ЭЛЕКТРОДВИГАТЕЛЬ ҚУВВАТИ	630 КВТ/СОАТ
7	ЭЛЕКТРОДВИГАТЕЛ АЙЛАНИШЛАР СОНИ	720 ОБ/МИН
8	БОСИМЛИ ҚУВУР ДИАМЕТРИ	1200 ММ
9	БОСИМЛИ ҚУВУР УЗУНЛИГИ	3,9 КМ
10	СУВ ОЛИШ МАНБАСИ	ҚАРШИ БОШ КАНАЛИ
11	БИРИКТИРИЛГАН МАЙДОН	ҚАРШИ ШАХАР

Figure 1. Opposite Head Channel PK 539.

This situation in itself entails reforms aimed at organizing the effective and rational use of existing water resources, improving the reclamation of irrigated lands, improving the technical condition of water farm facilities and their modernization, large-scale introduction of water saving technologies, strengthening the technical base of water management organizations, further improving the activities of water

consumer associations, improving the skills of It will be necessary to create the appropriate legal framework for the implementation of these tasks.

A huge amount is allocated from the state budget for the modernization of water management facilities. In the Republic, thousands of kilometers of trunk canals, pumping station avankamera, irrigation and nov networks, how many hydrotechnical structures and hydroposts are cleaned and repaired every year, and the technical condition is improved. As a result, rapid water management and timely guaranteed supply to consumers are provided, and losses to maintenance and filtration in irrigation networks are significantly reduced.

The "satellite" pumping station was built in 1981 for the purpose of providing irrigation water to the city of Qarshi, with the water source being the Qarshi main canal. The pumping station is equipped with 3 pumping units of the brand D 4500 – 95. The generating channel of the pumping station has the following parameters: the length of the channel is 22.2 m, the width at the bottom is 1.5 meters, the depth of filling the channel at the maximum current is 1.45 meters, and the slope is defined as 1.5.

Figure 1.1. Main building of the pumping station” satellite

The vanguard of the pumping station is made of monolithic concrete. The base of the reinforced concrete coating is a compacted grunt with a volumetric weight of up to 1.76 t / m³. The total length of the avankamera is 10.7 m, of which the initial part is 7.8 m and the slope is 0.2 towards the intake structure.

Figure 1.2 water intake point from the main channel against the satellite pumping station

The "satellite" pumping station D 4000-95 is equipped with horizontal centrifugal pumps. The design capacity of each unit is 1.1 m³/sec and the total capacity of the pumping station is 2.2 m³/sec.

The pump has the following specifications: Napor $n=48.5$ m, Power $Q = 4000$ m³/h, weight – 5.0 tons, rotation speed 720 ayl / min. Electrodivigatel brand-SD-2-85/57-8uxl has the following parameters: power – 630 kW, rotation speed 720 ayl / min., weight - 4.13 tons. The diameter of the pressure tubes is 1020 mm and their length is up to 3000 m.

There is a complex of drainage devices containing 6K-160-20 brand 2 pumps for pumping drainage and wastewater from the "satellite" pumping station. The satellite pumping station building plan and the ridge along the pumping station building are listed.

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